

Preparing documentation and adapting work processes for acquiring DSA

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Content

- 1) About ADP
- 2) Brief history of policy development
- 3) Changes → Challenges
- 4) Preparing, developing policy

Social Science Data Archives, University of Ljubljana

<http://www.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

- 1997
- national data repository for social sciences
- depositors from all 4 (3 public) universities, private research centres, Statistical Office of Slovenia (8-10 research centres per year)
- 600 social science surveys
- cca. 700 users yearly (90 % education, 10 % scientific/research purpose)
- ADP is the only research data repository in Slovenia

BRIEF HISTORY – ADP

From its start ADP follows developments in the field of data archiving

CESSDA

FDC

Involvement on national level – cooperation with libraries (National University Library, Central Technological Library at the UL, The University of Maribor Library)

2010 - 2014

Open access to the achievements of Slovenian scientists

Joint Conference of the Special Libraries Section and the Academic Libraries Section of the Slovenian Library Association

Social Science Data Archives and open data services in the Republic of Slovenia
(roles, responsibilities, trusted repositories) (15 p. article published in 2010)

Slovene conference on long-term preservation of digital material

Analysis of current situation and perspective of digital preservation in the Social Science Data Archives (ADP). (30 p. article published in 2011)

CONFERENCE NUK 2014

BRIEF HISTORY CESSDA TRUST

CESSDA TRUST Workshop 1 (Spring 2013)

CESSDA membership requirements – DSA!

SELF EVALUATION

(detecting missing documents / not well defined procedures)

CESSDA TRUST Workshop 2 (Autumn 2013)

- > decision to work on documents
- > Backup procedures
- > Outsourcing staff / servers

New Challenges

Internal Changes

- Staff – getting bigger, having more obligations due to inclusion in national /international projects
 - >Need to standardize internal processes / formalize work-flow
- Tools – develop more sophisticated tools (JIRA application on top of FEDORA)
 - >Backup procedures

External Changes (open access)

- EU level – H2020 (data + publication)
- SI-level [National strategy of open access to scientific publications and research data in Slovenia 2015-2020](#)
 - >Promotional activities (FOSTER, RDM)

Preparing Policy document

- In spring 2015 we established an internal DSA team
- Need to develop a crown document, which covers all aspects of ADP past, current and future work

s/serv-policy-development

Developing ADP Policy

Sources:

- [OAIS model](#)
- [Guidelines for the creation of an institutional policy on digital preservation authored and edited by the Nestor working group](#)
- [UK Data Archive Preservation Policy](#)
- [Documents and Materials for Social Science Digital Data \(SERSCIDA\)](#)
- CESSDA Statutes: Annex 2: Obligations of Service Providers

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Developing ADP Policy

TOPICS COVERED

- Purpose
- Scope and Objectives
- Requirements
- Legal and regulatory framework
- Roles and Responsibilities
- Model
- Preservation planning and strategy
- IT Architecture
- Security
- Co-operation
- Funding and Resource Planning

(source: UK Data Archive Preservation Policy)

Planning evaluation and updating every 2 years.

Working process

1. Description of the current state in ADP
2. Defining of missing points or critical steps in the workflow
 - We tried to find solutions / solve problems
 - If not, then further steps were planned

Challenges

- Preparing missing documents and publicly available information

For example: Access rules for secure data

-> safe room environment

REPUBLIKA SLOVENIJA
STATISTIČNI URAD RS

- Terminology issues → Only national data centre, developing terminology in cooperation with NUK and ARS; systematization of jobs (no data scientist, digital archivist)
- Long term sustainability
 - > National level (NUK, ARNES)
 - > CESSDA level (like [Data-PASS](#))

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